

Response paper 1

LAST NAME: TUMBA

FIRST NAME: RAYMOND

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INSTRUCTOR: DR KABIRU GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. American Vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
3. What is Style Guide, And Why Would I Need One? (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
4. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLID 2021, 58-64)
5. Sample Corrections to Papers (EUCLID 2021, 65-72)
- 6.

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1) INTRODUCTION

An English aphorism states, 'a journey of five hundred miles begins with a step.' With my knowledge of Classical Arabic and having hailed from Maiduguri Diocese, the headquarters of Boko Haram in Nigeria, I was overly pleased to launch myself into the Ph.D. program and study of Counter Terrorism and Deradicalisation. However, little did I realise that the first step would be a protracted one due to familiarising oneself with the world of ZETERO, the unique way of writing a response paper, and mainly due to other challenges. All these challenges are now water under the bridge as I have decided to give my all to get the best from the program.

This Response Paper will discuss the following fundamental concepts: American Vs. British English; Plagiarism; What is A Style Guide, And Why Would I Need One? Latin Abbreviations and Expressions and Sample Corrections to Papers.

2) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

Being privileged to attend St Peter's Minor Seminary, Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria, exposed me to the reality that there are seeming differences between American and British English. I could not fathom why our Form mistress (an Irish Rev. Sr) insisted that we place our tongue between our lips while pronouncing words like 'The, this, these, that, and those.' Coming to the U.K. made me realise why she did that. She wanted us to sound British and to stop rolling the letter 'R' in words like 'Lord, Mother, Father, and Sister.' We tend to imitate our science teacher, who had an American Accent. He never thrusts his tongue between his lips while pronouncing the words with 'TH' but rolls the 'R' in every word that contains the letter 'R.' American and British English are more similar than different, especially with educated English. While the words 'Axe/ Ax, Colour/ Color, and Plough/ Plow' are different in spelling, they have the same pronunciation, and words like 'Leisure,' 'Schedule,' and 'Dynasty' have the exact spelling, yet pronounced differently. (EUCLID 25).

I have used 'Commas' and 'Quotation Marks' interchangeably for years. However, it dawned on me that it is the British style to use inverted commas, for instance, 'The girl jumped the fence,' while American English uses quotation marks, thus, "The girl jumped the fence." (EUCLID 31).

3) PLAGIARISM

Sometimes back, a friend of mine worriedly called and confessed to me that he was threatened and warned by his university authority that he would be expelled from the United Kingdom university because he plagiarised the assignment he submitted. It is seriously considered a criminal offence in the U.K. 'Plagiarism is the utilisation of a source of information by the writer devoid of acknowledging the author of that source of information. It encompasses usurping someone else's word or ideas without crediting the author; or writing a project or thesis for someone.' (EUCLID 34).

The rationality in citing or acknowledging someone's work is that it is ethical, right, and fair and extricates one from committing a grievous academic blunder. The best way to eschew Plagiarism is simply by properly citing the source of the information. Citing could be 'In-text' which entails "citing the piece of work one uses within the actual text itself." (EUCLID 35) which could be via Quotations or paraphrases. Ideally, paraphrasing is commendable in a thesis, while long quotations should be imbibed minimally to depict the writer's originality.

4) WHAT IS STYLE GUIDE, AND WHY WOULD I NEED ONE?

"A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent." (EUCLID 41). For instance, in all my correspondence and academic writings during this program, EUCLID highly advocates that I use the Chicago Rules (Turabian) and that American English and British English are equally acceptable.

From all indications, the style guide is crucial for coherence and consistency. (EUCLID 41). In conformity with the style guide, I will strictly abide by the Euclide Genre

of academic writing; for example, in writing the Response Paper, I must follow all the instructions in the Templet of Response Paper.

A style guide is crucial because it guides both the moderator and the student. It will save lots of time in proofreading (EUCLID 42) and correction, while the corrections of the moderator will not take the student aback.

5) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

One of the Courses I studied for a degree in Philosophy was Latin. Studying Latin as a seminarian aspiring to the Catholic priesthood was a prerequisite and never optional. We learned that Latin is a dead language. By implication, it is not spoken anywhere in the world. However, we had to study Latin because important Church documents are written in Latin to maintain their original meaning. Though a dead language, Latin abbreviations are used in business, formal, and technical writing (EUCLID 59). Primary, secondary, and tertiary students also use them. Without a second thought, primary pupils say they attend school at 7:30 a.m. (Ante Meridien) and return home at 4:00 p.m. (Post Meridien). While writing, they equally use etc. (Et cetera). Before one is employed to work, one's C.V. (Curriculum Vitae) is crucially required.

Seminarians often spoke in Latin to express their intellectual prowess and sagacity, while others embellished their spoken English by adding Latin expressions. Some Latin expressions often used are: 'ab initio' (from the beginning). Ab initio, seminarians know that being a Catholic priest entails a life of sacrifice and it is a celibate life. 'Prima facie' (at first sight; on the face of it). Prima facie, the priesthood looks attractive, but 'inter alia' (among other things) is challenging. It is not 'pro tempore' (temporarily) but a life of 'ad infinite (never-ending). Such usage of Latin expressions is not only peculiar among seminarians, law students, and lawyers equally utilise them both in writing and speaking. For instance, 'I am doing the case 'pro bono' (for the public good, at no cost)'; 'Let us maintain the 'status quo' (things as they are).' 'The exam is 'viva (voce)' (oral examination)' (EUCLID 63).

The Latin expression 'quid pro quo' (something in return) (EUCLID 63) is one of the expressions that tickles my fancy, but I have never used it orally or in writing. I will not hesitate to use it confidently from now on.

6) SAMPLE CORRECTIONS TO PAPERS

'It is not a mistake to make a mistake, but a mistake to repeat it. To avoid repeating basic mistakes in writing the Response Paper, EUCLID depicted how the Response Paper is marked and how it should be. Some of the primary mistakes are leaving a space after opening a bracket before the first word, repeating the same word twice, and using different fonts, tautology, and word contractions. (EUCLID 66-70).

A Response Paper should begin with an Introduction, followed by the selected concepts (about 5 to 7 concepts) from the assignment materials, and end with a conclusion.

7) **CONCLUSION**

This first session was very informative and enriching because it exposed me to what I anticipate as a Ph.D. student and to the basic tools I will need to accomplish this academic program. It has glitches of mixed feelings and procrastination from my side. However, with determination and cognisance of what is expected of me to scale through with this program, the hesitation has been put aside, and I intend to face the program with great enthusiasm and optimism.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.